

Survey Questions

The following questions were included in the survey sent to academics regarding the contextualized materials developed.

1. Do you think there is a need to develop computing education materials that are contextually relevant to Africa? Why or why not?
2. Having reviewed the sample materials that have been created by our team so far, do you think they will be useful for your class? Why or why not?
3. What are some of the strengths of the materials that have been created so far?
4. What are some of the shortcomings or weaknesses of the materials created so far? How can they be improved?
5. What programming language is used in the ``CS1" course that you teach?
6. Which of the following learning outcomes (as described in the ACM computing curriculum guidelines) are addressed by your course? (Note that it is not expected that all learning outcomes below are addressed). [For each one, respondents could indicate if it is ``Not Addressed", ``Partially Addressed" or ``Fully Addressed".]
 - a. Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements.
 - b. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing.
 - c. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
 - d. Develop programs that use file I/O to provide data persistence across multiple executions.
 - e. Develop programs that create simple classes and instantiate objects of those classes (if supported by the language).
 - f. Read a given program and explain what it does.
 - g. Write comments for a program or a module specifying what it does.
 - h. Trace the flow of control during the execution of a program.
 - i. Use appropriate terminology to identify elements of a program (e.g., identifier, operator, operand)
 - j. Write programs that work with text by using string processing capabilities provided by the language.
 - k. Develop tests for modules, and apply a variety of strategies to design test cases.
 - l. Explain some limitations of testing programs.
 - m. Build, execute and debug programs using a modern IDE and associated tools such as visual debuggers.
 - n. Apply basic programming style guidelines to aid readability of programs such as comments, indentation, proper naming of variables, etc.
 - o. Write specifications of a module as module comment describing its functionality.
7. In what country is your university located?
8. Is your institution public or private?
9. Do you have students from African countries other than the one in which your university is located? (i.e. international students from other African countries)

10. If you have international students in your course, what are some of the countries represented?
11. In what degree programmes are the students who take your class enrolled? (select all that apply)
 - Computer Science
 - Information Systems
 - Information Technology
 - Computer Engineering
 - Other
12. In what year of university are the majority of students who take your class?
 - Year 1
 - Year 2
 - Other
13. Additional general comments about the materials, the project, this survey, or your class.